

Object Oriented DBMSs using GIS Data

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Abstract

Data management and organization have become so complex and challenging in today's electronic age of information. In the last decade major changes have occurred in the database domain, as the result of increased interest to non-traditional database applications such as multimedia, office automation, CAD, CASE, GIS, Web databases, and others. In contrast to the relational era, the current database world is more diverse and showing contradictory tendencies. On the one hand, vendors of popular relational database management systems (DBMS), such as IBM, Informix and Oracle, extend their products with new capabilities, including support for non-traditional data types (text, graphics, sound, video, spatial data, etc.) and for object-oriented concepts, such as ADT-s, classes and inheritance. Independently, the Object Data Management Group (ODMG) proposes a standard based on a pure object model. A lot of research and development from the industry and academia is devoted to various aspects of object-relational and object-oriented DBMS. Much has been said about object orientation, and how it should change the face of information technology. But what would be the real benefits of using an object-oriented GIS? Basic concepts in object technology, such as inheritance, polymorphism and encapsulation are reviewed, and their meaning is transported to the needs of a GIS.

Key word: DBMS, OODBMS, GIS, Object orientation

Introduction

The field of object-oriented databases (object bases) has emerged as the convergence of several research and development threads, including new tendencies in object-oriented programming languages, software engineering, multimedia, distributed systems, Web, as well as the traditional relational database technologies. Object-oriented databases make up several views. The most popular view is that the databases consist of objects rather than relations, tables or other data structures. The concept of "object" is a kind of idiom. Object-orientedness in computer technologies, from the psychological point of view, is founded on inborn mechanisms of our minds, as the idea of a computer keyboard is based on the anatomic fact that humans have hands and fingers.

The object-orientedness, which follows the natural human psychology, is considered as a new hope to reduce the complexity; in consequence, to reduce the software crisis. This is supposed to be achieved by reducing the distance between the human perception of the problem (business) domain, an abstract conceptual model of the problem domain (expressed, e.g., as a class diagram), and the programmer's view of data structures and operations.

The abstraction of concepts and entities that can be found in the real world is an important part of the creation of information systems. Moreover, the success of a computer implementation of an information system depends on how well the real world entities and their interactions are transposed to a computer database. Abstraction functions as a tool to help us comprehend the system, by dividing it in separate components that are viewed in different levels of complexity and detail, according to the need to understand and represent the various real world entities and their interactions. The need for better abstraction tools in database management systems (DBMS) is one of the determinant factors of the development of object-oriented technology.

A relational database stores relations. In practical terms, storing relations means storing data items (in a table) that are related or logically "connected" in some way. So, for example, a person's name is logically connected to that person's address ... so a customer table would store

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(among other things) the relation between the person's name and address. It would do that by (again, in practical terms) putting those items together in the same row of the same table.

To put objects into relational databases, they must be described in terms of simple string, integer, or real number data. An object database stores objects. Meanwhile, in an object database, the relations are inherent in the structure of the objects themselves.

Object database systems combine the classical capabilities of relational database management systems (RDBMS), with new functionalities assumed by the object-orientedness. The traditional capabilities include:

Secondary storage management

- Schema management
- Concurrency control
- Transaction management, recovery
- Query processing
- Access authorization and control, safety, security
- New capabilities of object databases include:

Complex objects

- Object identities
- User-defined types
- Encapsulation
- Type/class hierarchy with inheritance
- Overloading, overriding, late binding, polymorphism
- Computational and pragmatic completeness of programmers' interfaces

The wave of pure object-oriented DBMS, which abandons assumptions of the relational database model, started in 1983, when Maier and Copeland presented a database management system with the data model of Smalltalk. From that time many research prototypes and commercial systems have been developed, among them Gemstone, ObjectStore, Versant, O2, Objectivity/DB, Poet, and others.

Object-Oriented Concepts

Object-oriented database models adopt the concepts of object-oriented programming languages. Actually, there is no agreement concerning their precise definition. The definitions presented below are most typical

Complex objects and object identity. The database should consist of objects having arbitrary complexity and an arbitrary number of hierarchy levels. Objects can be aggregates of (sub-) objects. Each database object has identity, i.e. a unique *internal* identifier (OID) (with no meaning in the problem domain).

Relationships, associations and links. Objects are connected by conceptual links. For instance, the *Employee* and *Department* objects can be connected by a link *worksFor*.

Encapsulation and information hiding. The internal properties of an object are subdivided into two parts: public (visible from the outside) and private (invisible from the outside).

Classes, types, interface. Each object is an instance of one or more classes. The class is understood as a blueprint for objects; i.e. objects are instantiated according to information presented in the class and the class contains the properties that are common for some collection of objects (objects' invariants).

Abstract data types (ADTs). A kind of a class, which assumes that any access to an object is limited to the predefined collection of operations.

Operations, methods and messages. An object is associated with a set of operations (called methods). The object performs the operation after receiving a message with the name of operation to be performed (and parameters of this operation).

Inheritance. Classes are organized in a hierarchy reflecting the hierarchy of real world concepts. For instance, the class *Person* is a super class of the classes *Employee* and *Student*. Properties of more abstract classes are inherited by more specific classes. Multi-inheritance means that a specific class inherits from several independent classes.

Polymorphism, late binding, and overriding. The operation to be executed on an object is chosen dynamically, after the object receives the message with the operation name. The same message sent to different objects can invoke different operations.

Persistence. Database objects are persistent, i.e., they live as long as necessary. They can outlive programs, which created these objects.

Technical details assumed by designers in particular models, languages and products make concepts with the same name (class, type, ADT, etc.) technically and practically very different.

Advanced Database (OODBMS) Applications

The computer industry has seen significant changes in the last decade. In database systems, RDBMSs have widespread acceptance for traditional business applications such as order processing, inventory control, banking, and airline reservations. However, existing RDBMSs have proven inadequate for applications whose needs are quite different from those of traditional business database applications. These applications include:

- computer – aided design (CAD);
- computer _ aided manufacturing (CAM);
- computer_aided software engineering (CASE);
- network management systems;
- office information systems (OIS) and multimedia systems;
- digital publishing;
- geographic information systems (GIS);
- interactive and dynamic Web sites.

Architecture of Object-Oriented DBMS

There are several concepts of the OODBMS architecture. The most abstract is the ANSI/SPARC architecture, which assumes three layers: the external user layer, the layer of a conceptual schema, and the layer of physical data. Another architecture is client/server, where database applications are subdivided into two parts: the database server (executing e.g. SQL statements sent by clients) and one or more clients sending requests to the server. More advanced are the three-tier architecture and multi-tier architecture, where layers (tiers) of a user interface and a database are separated by one (or more) layers devoted to business logic. From the functional point of view, a typical OODBMS architecture is presented in (Figure 1).

Figure 1. The architecture of Map Query for RDBMS and OODBMS using GIS data

ODMG Standard

Object Data Management Group (ODMG) was founded by a group of startup companies who thought that traditional standard-making processes were slow and cumbersome and that they could do better. They got their first publication (ODMG-93) out very quickly, then discovered that making real standards is actually very hard work. They also set expectations far too high, by announcing that all the members were committed to delivering conforming implementations by the end of 1994. Few professionals believed them, but of course, it was part of the game. Till now, there is no evidence that (except O2) the standard is fully implemented by other ODMG members.

The ODMG standard (version ODMG 2.0 [ODMG97]) consists of the following parts:

Object Model. It determines the meaning of basic concepts of object-oriented data structures, such as: objects, attributes, relationships, collections, classes, interfaces, operations, inheritance, encapsulation, and others. It is intended to be independent of any programming language as far as possible. The object model assumes strong typing and orthogonal combination of type constructors. It defines also collections, such as sets, bags, sequences, arrays and dictionaries, and other concepts.

Object Definition Language (ODL). Both the object model and ODL are extensions of the corresponding parts of the OMG CORBA standard. ODL is an extension of CORBA IDL. ODL is used to determine the structure of a database, i.e., a database schema. The schema is necessary to understand what the database contains and how is organized. An ODL schema determines collections of objects, relationships between objects, object attributes, operations that can be applied to the objects, exceptions that can be caused by these operations. ODL is neutral to programming languages (though follows the C++ syntax).

Object Interchange Format. It determines the representation of objects for exchanging them between different OODBMS.

Object Query Language (OQL). The language is claimed to be a compatible extension of the SQL standard, but actually OQL retains some syntactic patterns of SQL only. Semantically,

OQL is very different from SQL, mainly because it follows the ODMG object model, which is essentially incompatible with the relational model. OQL is intended to retrieve data from an object base.

Bindings to programming languages C++, Smaltalk, Java, .Net etc. The bindings determine principles of including ODL and OQL statements as constructs of the mentioned above programming languages. Besides, the bindings define many classes (written in the syntax of a particular programming language), allowing to access and process an object base directly from an application written in one of the mentioned languages.

Object-Based Data Model for GIS

Object-oriented technology has impacted many fields for more than two decades. User interface such as the windows environment is perhaps the most obvious application example of object oriented technology. Popular GIS software packages such as MapInfo and ArcView have also incorporated object-oriented technology into the user interface design and the macro language. The introduction of geodatabase data model by ESRI, Inc. In 1999 is different from previous applications of object-oriented technology in GIS. It represents a new beginning, at least for ESRI products, of embracing an object-based rather than a georelational, data model. The geodatabase data model may have also promoted increased research activities in developing complete object-based modes.

The object-based data model treats spatial data as objects. An object can represent a spatial feature such as a road, a timber stand, or a hydrologic unit. An object can also represent a road layer or the coordinate system that the road layer is based on. In fact, almost everything work with in GIS can be represented as an object. The object-based data model differs from the georelational data model in two important aspects. First, the object-based data model stores both the spatial and attribute data of spatial features in a single system rather than a split system. The spatial data are stored in a special field along with other fields for attribute data. Second, the object-based data model allows a spatial feature to be associated with a set of properties and methods. A property describes an attribute or characteristic of an object. A property describes and attribute or characteristic of an object. A method performs a specific action.

Classes

A class is a set of objects with similar attributes. Unless objects are organized into some hierarchical structure, the management of properties and methods in a GIS can become difficult, if not impossible. Operationally, a class defines the properties and methods of objects that are members of the class, For example, a class called feature can cover point, line, and polygon feature objects. The features class defines the same properties (e.g., delete) for all three types of objects; the three feature types of point, line, and polygon are grouped in the same class through generalization. Specialization, on the other hand, differentiates objects of a given class by an attribute or attributes. For example, geometry can differentiate the three feature types (Figure 2).The use of generalization and specialization therefore creates a hierarchical structure, in which objects are grouped into classes and classes are grouped into superclasses and subclasses.

Figure 2. The Geometry property of the Feature class can differentiate the object types of point, line, and polygon

Relationships between Classes

The object-oriented software design literature has suggested the relationships of association, composition, type inheritance, and instantiation that can be established between classes (Larman 1997; Zeiler 1999)

Association defines how many instances of one class can be associated with the other class through multiplicity expressions at both ends of the relationship. Common multiplicity expressions are on (default), and one or more (1.*) For example, a street can be associated with one or more signal lights but it can only be associated with one coordinate system (Figure 3).

Aggregation describes the whole part relationship between classes. Aggregation is a type of association except that the multiplicity at the composite (“whole”) end is typically 1 and multiplicity at the other (“part”) end is zero or any positive integer. For example, a census tract is an aggregate of a number of census blocks.

Composition is similar to aggregating in that the multiplicity at the composite end is 1 and the multiplicity at the other end is zero or any positive integer. But the composite in a composition relationship solely owns the part. For example, a high way can have zero or any number of roadside rest areas. The highway controls the lifetime of the roadside rest area.

Figure 3. Two examples of class associations

Figure 4. An example of type inheritance

Figure 5. An example of instantiation

Type inheritance defines the relationship between a superclass and a subclass. A subclass is a member of a super class and inherits the properties and methods of the superclass. But a subclass can have additional properties and methods to separate itself from other members of the superclass. For example, residential area is a member of built-up area but it can have properties such as lot size that separate residential area from commercial or industrial area (Figure 4). Instantiation means that an object of a class can be created from an object of another class. For example, a high-density residential area object can be created from a residential area object (Figure 5).

Query Languages

The commercial success of the relational model and relational database systems to a big extent has been amplified by the idea of query languages. Initially, query languages addressed a non-experienced user, who needed a simple mean for making *ad hoc* reports from the database and for performing simple updating operations. Query languages should have the following properties:

- High abstraction level: avoiding details of physical data organization (including the presence of indices).
- Non-procedurality or declarativity: expressing directly the goal of computations rather than actions leading to the goal.
- Macroscopic operations: quasi-parallel operations on many data.
- Natural way of expressing users' requests.
- Efficiency: executing queries in reasonable time (which implies the necessity of powerful query optimization).
- Universality: the ability to express majority of user requests.
- Domain independence: a query language is a generic part of the system, not biased towards particular application domain.
- Interpreted and dynamically bound: the possibility to execute queries immediately, with no compilation and linking stages.
- Some new idea in this respect is presented by a research line, which postulates building an integrated query and programming language.

```

using System;
using System.Collections.Generic;
using System.Linq;
using System.Text;
namespace MapQuery.OODBCClasses
{
    class MapInfo
    {
        int map_id;
        double area_Inmeter;
        string map_url;
        string area_name;
        public MapInfo(int mid, double ameter, string mur1, string aname)
        {
            map_id = mid;
            area_Inmeter = ameter;
            map_url = mur1;
            area_name = aname;
        }
    }
}
  
```

```

    }

    public int MapID
    {
        get { return map_id; }
        set { map_id = value; }
    }
    public string AreaName
    {
        get { return area_name; }
        set { area_name = value; }
    }
}
}
}

```

This research is carried on by map query for Yangon division of some townships. For example Ahlone and Bahan of Geographic Information System(GIS) data of map query and its attributes data extract by OQL language.

```

using System;
using System.Collections.Generic;
using System.Linq;
using System.Text;
using Db4objects.Db4o;
namespace MapQuery.OODBClasses
{
    class OODB
    {
        string dbfile;
        IObjectContainer db;
        MapInfo mapinfo;
        public OODB()
        {
            dbfile = @"C:\OODB\MapDB.db4o";
            db = Db4oEmbedded.OpenFile(dbfile);
        }
        public void Save(int mid,double ameter,string murl,string aname)
        {
            MapInfo mapinfo = new MapInfo(mid, ameter, murl, aname);
            db.Store(mapinfo);
            db.Commit();
            db.Close();
        }
        public IObjectSet Query(string aname)
        {
            // string query = "Select * from MapInfoTable where AreaName=@areaname";
            MapInfo mapinfo = new MapInfo(0, 0.0, null, aname);
            IObjectSet result = db.QueryByExample(mapinfo);

            return result;        }
    }
}

```

Object Query Language for part of Yangon division(some township) GIS map using db4o database.

Conclusion

This paper is represented a synthesis of an object oriented data model based on the abstraction concept of classification, generalization, association and aggregation. Inheritance and propagation are crucial for modeling the behavior of complex object. It has been demonstrated how object modeling can serve as suitable method for the design of spatial

information system. Current data model and database technology are not sufficient for the specific tasks of dealing with large amount of spatial data.

Future GIS are excellent candidates for applying object-oriented concepts in order to improve their design, implementation, and maintenance. All three object-oriented concepts data modeling, software engineering, and database management systems are important for GIS personal.

Object databases have already a position on the market, which is permanently growing. Despite a lot of commercial confusion and despite the object-relational rivals, object databases are already successfully applied in various practical areas. Although the current market segment of pure object databases is not bigger than 5%, there are many symptoms showing that this situation is changing.

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